

**PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND MECHANISM: ITS RELATION
TO THE LEARNER'S OUTCOME AS MEDIATED
BY SELF-CONFIDENCE**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 6

Pages: 649-665

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2088

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12797862

Manuscript Accepted: 06-13-2024

Parental Involvement and Mechanism: Its Relation to the Learner's Outcome as Mediated by Self-Confidence

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Abstract

Child's learning acquisition is greatly influence by parental involvement and mechanisms. Parental involvement is a multifaceted activity which represents many different parental behaviors and parenting practices such as parental aspiration for their child's academic achievement, parental communication with their children about school, parental participation in school activities, parental communications with teachers about their child, and parental rules at home which are considered education related. Republic Act No. 9155 otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 under section 1.2 stated that the parents and the community shall be encouraged for active involvement in the education of the child. This study works on determining the relationship of parental involvement and mechanisms on child's learning outcomes through the collection of data using survey questionnaire and utilization of descriptive correlational research design. Moreover, Pearson's R was used in treating the data collected. It was revealed that a significant relationship among variables were observed however weak relationship between learning at home with creativity and presentation was determined. Moreover, indirect relationship between parental mechanisms and quarterly tests was revealed. Additionally, no significant relationship between learning outcomes and self-confidence was seen. Lastly, a weak to moderate significant relationship between self-confidence and parental involvement and parental mechanisms was exhibited. This led to the idea that variables have little to negative relationships especially parental mechanisms an quarterly scores results as well as learning outcomes and self-confidence. Due to this, it is recommended that strong connection between parents and child should be established to strengthen and further increase the positive learning outcomes. Monitoring of student success in doing their work is also encouraged to be practiced by parents to build child support and confidence.

Keywords: *parental involvement, parental mechanisms, learning outcomes*

Introduction

A child's character, values, beliefs, skills and knowledge are believed to be nurtured and influenced by their first teachers, their parents. This significant role of parents contributes greatly to the well-being of their child. Thus, their involvement, parentings styles and practices especially in connection to education are said to be predictors of a child's successes and achievements in several aspects of their lives (Jesse, 2013).

Parental involvement as classified by Harris and Goodall (2007) is a multifaceted activity which represents various parental attitudes and behaviors which also includes parenting style and practices such as parental aspiration for child's development in terms of academics, communication to schools regarding child's performance, parents' active participation in school related activities, parents and teachers dialogue and communication all of these which are essential to child's education.

Policies and laws have viewed the essential role of parents in the success and attainment of the educational goals parallel to the national agenda. Republic Act No. 9155 otherwise known as the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 under section 1.2 reiterates that parents and child's community should go hand in hand in child-rearing. The participation of educational stakeholders should be maximized. Due to this, the Department of Education (DepEd) had ordered the initiatives of parent-teacher conferences every quarter through the DepEd Order No. 23, series of 2016 found on enclosure no. 2.

This is envisioned to describe to the parents advancement or improvement of their child in the school, which is also looked at to elevate parents' involvement in school-related activities. This partnership, stated on the law, has given parental involvement high priority as a contributing factor that will harness and develop students' skills, performance and achievements.

Hence, parental involvement in schools is not just attending homeroom and PTA conferences. Students in different groups and grades perform significantly when their parents' support on their education is visible. With this, the researcher would like to dig deeper on the concepts and influence of parental involvement to the students especially on their level of cookery skills. This study will serve as a great avenue for learners, parents and teachers to understand each role and involvement in attaining not just the educational objectives but also in honing a capable, skilled and holistic learner.

Despite the effort of the Department of Education (DepEd), thru the school administration and its teachers, in involving parents on school activities to elevate the academic performance and behaviour of learners, it is an undeniable fact that several factors are hindering the active involvement of parents on their child's performance. Deteriorating number of parent's participation in school is notably alarming especially when students reach higher grade level. Lower number of parents attending PTA meetings is recorded.

Meanwhile, it was observed that most students on the Cookery specialization would always seek support, guidance and involvement

from their parents especially in fulfilling the activities required on their performance tasks. These include them supporting students' needs on additional knowledge in enhancing their cooking skills as well as their support financially to be able to afford necessary ingredients for each assigned dish. Oftentimes, this difficulty in finding support and involvement from their parents would force the students to shift specialization.

It is in this light that the researcher has seen the essence of conducting a work on determining the impact of involvement of parents in students' level of cookery skills. This study to be undertaken will also aim to provide avenue for the researcher to ascertain the relationship between parental involvement and the level of cookery skills of the Grade 9 students. The outcome of this study will serve as a guide in crafting activities focused on increasing and maximizing parental involvement on their child's life not just at home but also at school.

Research Questions

This study seeks to understand and analyze the relationship between parental involvement and mechanism on the learners' outcomes. Specifically, it sought to answers the following questions:

1. What is profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. number of siblings;
 - 1.4. parents' educational attainment;
 - 1.4.1. fathers' Educational Attainment;
 - 1.4.2. mothers' Educational Attainment;
 - 1.5. Parents' occupation
 - 1.5.1. Father's occupation;
 - 1.5.2. Mother's occupation; and
 - 1.6. family monthly income?
2. How may the level of parental involvement to the students be described in terms of:
 - 2.1. parenting;
 - 2.2. communicating;
 - 2.3. volunteering;
 - 2.4. learning at home;
 - 2.5. decision making; and
 - 2.6. collaborating with community?
3. How may parental involvement and parental mechanism be described in terms of:
 - 3.1. parental encouragement;
 - 3.2. parental modelling;
 - 3.3. parental reinforcement; and
 - 3.4. parental instructions
4. What is the self- confidence level of the students?
5. What is the learner's outcome in terms of:
 - 5.1. Quarterly Test
 - 5.2. Performance Task
6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest of the control group and experimental in reading comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency?
 - 6.1. Parental Involvement
 - 6.2. Parental Mechanism
7. Is there a significant relationship between self-confidence and learners' outcome?
8. Is there significant relationship between students' self-confidence in terms
 - 8.1. Parental Involvement
 - 8.2. Parental Mechanism
9. Is the students' self-confidence mediate the relationship between parental involvement and mechanism to learners' outcome?

Methodology

Research Design

Data collected in this study were primarily and mostly quantitative in nature thus it is imperative to utilize a quantitative research design. According to Creswell (2014), this type of research involves the collection of numerical data and application of statistical analysis. Specifically, this paper sought to determine if significant relationships exists between variables: parental involvement and mechanism and the level of cookery skills. In order to determine the relationship between the aforementioned variables, this work

applied a correlational research design.

A correlational research design is the most appropriate when establishing associations between variables or concepts as explained by Tan (2014). Relationship as determined may display an increase or decrease based from the degree of relationship between the two. It should also be noted that direction of changes is also considered when establishing relationships.

This correlational research design employed to determine and analyze if how parental involvement significance.

Respondents

In relation with the focus of this endeavor, the researcher's main respondents were the grade 9 students of Malaking Pulo National High School and Pantay Integrated High School who are taking Cookery as their specialization and currently enrolled in the school year 2023-2024.

In identifying the sample, the researcher applied a purposive sampling. Adler and Clark (2018) discussed that this type of sampling requires a clear and specific criteria of whom were included in the sample. Criteria and characteristics were set in order to select and filter the respondents. In this study, the researcher set the criteria as the following (1) must be a Grade 9 cookery student and (2) enrolled in the current school year (2023-2024) either in Malaking Pulo National High School or Pantay Integrated High School.

Table 1. *The distribution of respondents in each school*

<i>School</i>	<i>Actual Respondents</i>
Malaking Pulo National High School	44
Pantay Integrated High School	56
Total	100

Instruments

The researcher performed intensive review of literature in order to select and filter the most appropriate questionnaire for the study. The selected questionnaire is in a Likert Scale type where interpretations ranged from 1 to 4.

The tool that was used by the researcher was consist of the three parts. The first part was allotted to determine the personal profile of the students. On the second part, the researcher included the questions relate to determination of the parental involvement while the last part was a test aimed to assess the cookery skills of the respondents.

A researcher-made test being was used in assessing the cookery skills of the students, items included were anchored on the competencies and standards set by the Department of Education.

The researcher conducted an intensive review of literature in order to come up an construct the appropriate questionnaire deemed aligned with the purpose of the study. Literatures were screened based from the alignment to the study and as part of the selection and development of the instrument. Item statements that included in the instruments was analyzed and examined to further confirm its content.

In order to establish the reliability of the instrument, a pilot administration test-retest reliability was done to a select non-participating students. On the other hand, for the validity of the material it was validated by Master Teacher in Technology and Livelihood Education for content analysis while Research Coordinator and experts for the construction of the tool. Content, construct, and face validity of the material was checked. Comments, recommendations, and suggestions of the experts was considered to further developed the validity of the instrument adapted.

Procedure

This research aims to determine and analyze the extent of the impact of parental involvement to the cookery skills of the respondents. Additionally, it also seeks to know the degree of relationship between the two variables. In the conduct of this study, the researcher was consistently follow the discussed procedure.

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter of intent and permission to the Schools Division Superintendent and Senior Education Program Specialist in Research and Planning. Once the letter was approved and signed, the researcher distributed the questionnaires to the respondents. In compliance with research ethics, the researcher made a letter of consent and assent asking the approval of the participants and their guardians to be part of the study. The said consent was included a short letter stating the scope and purpose of the study. Furthermore, the researcher strictly adhered to research ethics by observing anonymity of participants, confidentiality of results and voluntary participations.

The participants of the study was given of at most of 1 week in completing the questionnaire before collection. Retrieval of the questionnaire followed by tabulation, analysis and interpretation of the obtained data.

Data Analysis

Data obtained was subjected to careful selection of statistical treatment after the data has been tabulated and analyzed. The results of

the data were interpreted. The enumerated statistical treatment was applied in the study.

General Weighted Mean – This was employed to describe the extent of the parental involvement.

Frequency and Percentage – These statistical analyses were applied to determine the number of respondents and their corresponding percentage in terms of their profile.

Pearson r – This was applied to see if significant relationship exist between parental involvement and cookery skills.

Results and Discussion

This section presents and interprets the data collected through the survey by using generally accepted statistical tools and concepts. Primary sources of the data for this study came from survey questionnaires distributed to the Grade 9 students of Malaking Pulo National High School and Pantay Integrated High School. The presentation of data follows the order of the statement of the problem posited earlier in this study.

Table 2. *Distribution of the respondents as to age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
13	1	1.0
14	83	83.0
15	15	15.0
17	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2 illustrates the data gathered by the researcher in connection to the age of the respondents. It could be gleaned from the table that most of the respondents are of age 14 years old wherein it composes 83% of the total number of respondents. Meanwhile, there is 1% noted respondent with the age 13, 15% for age 15 and lastly, 1% for a respondent age 17. This imply that most of the respondents are in Grade 9 as the Philippine Educational System set ages 14-15 for Grade 9 or third year of the Junior High School. These respondents were carefully selected to fit the purpose of this study. Likewise, the researcher deemed the respondents appropriate for the study as these are students taking up TLE with the specialization on cookery.

As utilized in this study, students whose age fall under the bracket of grade 9 are the most appropriate to be respondents of this study. As prescribed by the Department of Education (DepEd), grade 9 students are to take Cookery as their specialization subject in Technology and Livelihood Education. This is designed to develop students' knowledge, skills, and attitude in the performance of Cookery tasks.

Likewise, Lavelle et al (2016) supported these findings as they claim that learning cooking skills as a child or teenage is shown to be positively related to their current use of cooking and food skills, cooking practices, cooking attitude and diet quality. This justifies that students who are taking cookery class may further develop their skills in cooking which was then assessed in this study through various parameters.

Table 3. *Distribution of the respondents as to Sex*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
1-Female	54	54.0
2-Male	46	46.0
Total	100	100.0

Depicted on Table 3 are the data collected, computed and tabulated to determine the sex of the selected respondents. It could be observed on the table that exceeding half of the total percentage of respondents or 54% are female. Meanwhile, 46% of the remaining percentage are male students taking cookery as their specialization in Technology Livelihood Education (TLE). It signifies that female are more likely to take cookery in TLE than male. It could also mean that more females are becoming more interested in cookery rather than male.

According to Temizkan and Uslu (2023), the number of women in the cooking profession is low. It was justified that although kitchens have traditionally been the domain of women, it is seen that the number of female cooks in the industrial kitchen is very few compared to male cooks today. Analyzing the data obtained, there is still a greater number of female respondents taking cookery as their TLE specialization. Hence, there is a noticeably few differences of the number of interested students in the subject when compared.

Table 4. *Distribution of the respondents as to number of siblings*

<i>Number of Siblings</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
0-3	69	69.0
4-6	22	22.0
7 or more	9	9.0
Total	100	100.0

Presented in Table 4 are the data on the number of siblings of the respondents. It could be gleaned from the table that most of the respondents have 0 – 3 number of siblings as it receives 69% of the total number of respondents. However, 22% of the respondents have 4 – 6 number of siblings in the family. Lastly, there are reported 9% respondents who claimed to have 7 or more number of siblings in the family. With these data, it could mean that most of the respondents do not compose a large family size as they could have a maximum of 5 members in the family including the parents.

Darko – Asumadu and Sika – Bright found in their study that family size, relative to the number of siblings in the family, and parental involvement significantly influenced the academic performance of the students. This may mean that parental involvement may be affected by the the number of siblings in the family. Hence, this would latter influence academic performance of the students or the learner in the family.

Table 5. Distribution of respondents according to Parents Educational Attainment

<i>Fathers' Educational Attainment</i>			<i>Mothers' Educational Attainment</i>	
<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Elementary	1	1	2	2
Undergraduate				
Elementary Graduate	7	7	2	2
High School	9	9	7	7
Undergraduate				
High School Graduate	49	49	54	54
Bachelor's Degree	14	14	16	16
Post-Baccalaureate	2	2	1	1
Degree				
Master's Degree	3	3	2	2
Post-Master's Degree	2	2	-	-
Others	13	13	16	16
Total	100	100	100	100

Table 5 presents the fathers' educational attainment of the respondents. It could be gleaned on the table that the highest percentage of 49% falls on the fathers who are high school graduates. There are also noted 14% respondents whose fathers earned bachelor's degree. Consequently, 13% of the respondents answered others on their choice of fathers' educational attainment. The least on the rank are recorded on elementary undergraduate which obtained 1% of the total percentage of respondents. Remarkably, there is 2% respondents whose fathers obtained post-master's degree. These data signifies that the student - respondents' parents are mostly high school graduates hence, there are still high numbers of fathers who earned higher degrees after high school.

Aligning these findings to the study conducted by Williams and Sanchez (2011), it was claimed that there are certain barriers that hinders parental involvement. These includes limited school background of parents as it prevents them in communicating with schools. Hence, Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) further noted that parental involvement is more important to children's academic success than their family's socioeconomic status, race, ethnicity or educational background.

Illustrated in Table 5 also are the data obtained relative to mothers' educational attainment. It could be noted from the table that a high percentage of 54% is noted on mothers who are high school graduates. However, least on the rank is 1% noted percentage on respondent whose mother obtained post – baccalaureate degree. It could also be observed that there is an equal percentage of mothers who obtained bachelor's degree and other educational attainment specified by the respondents. The data tabulated imply that there are still high percentage of mothers who earned higher degree after their bachelor's degree.

Relative to parents' educational attainment, Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) stated that parental involvement is more important to children's academic success than their family's socioeconomic status, race, ethnicity, or educational background. This proves that one's educational background may not affect students' academic progress and success hence, parental involvement significantly affects students' academic performance.

Table 6. Distribution of respondents according to Parents Occupation

<i>Fathers' Occupation</i>			<i>Mothers' Occupation</i>	
<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Permanent	45	45	30	30
Contractual	23	23	16	16
Self-Employed	16	16	20	20
Unemployed	16	16	34	34
Total	100	100	100	100

Table 6 illustrates the respondents’ parents’ occupation specifically their fathers’ occupation. The data reveal that most of the respondents’ father have permanent jobs as it obtained a percentage of 45% out of the total number of respondents. Second to the rank represents 23% of the fathers’ who have contractual jobs at the time of this study was conducted. Meanwhile, there are similar percentage obtained by self-employed and unemployed fathers of the respondents. The data imply that most of the respondents are capable of being supported by their parents in terms of their needs on the subject like ingredients, supplies and the like.

Hence, Ho (2009) stated in his study that today’s parents are preoccupied with the distractions and demands of daily life which may hinder parental involvement. These include low-income and inflexible work hours since most of the parents of the respondents are working on a permanent job, it is burdensome to attend school activities or participate in the schooling of their children on a regular basis.

Illustrated in Table 6 also are the data obtained on the respondents’ mothers’ occupation. Varying data reveals that most of the mothers are unemployed as it garnered 34% of the total number of respondents. Meanwhile, there are still 30% of the respondents whose mothers secured a permanent job. Least among the data are the self-employed mothers with 20% and 16% are for contractual. This may signify that most mothers are housewives who are in-charge of their homes as they are unemployed at the time that this study was conducted.

This conclusion was supported by the study of Lavelle et al (2016) where they found that the mother was the most commonly named source for past learning whereas learning from the mother only was linked with greater level of cooking and better dietary practices. This may also justify that with the larger number of mothers who are unemployed, parental involvement on their children are better exhibited.

Table 7. Distribution of the respondents as to Family Monthly Income

<i>Family Income</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Below Php 5,000	22	22.0
Php 5, 001 – 10, 000	27	27.0
Php 10, 001 – 15, 000	32	32.0
Php 15, 000 and above	19	19.0
Total	100	100.0

Data on Table 7 illustrates the family monthly income of the respondents. It could be observed that most of the respondents receives a family income ranging from 10, 001 to 15,000 wherein it obtained the highest percentage of 32%. Second on the rank garnered 27% of the total respondents implying that they receive a monthly family income of 5,001 – 10, 000. Thirdly, 22% of the respondents answered that they received below 5000 family income making 15,000 and above least on the rank as it only obtained 19% of the total percentage. It could be perceived from the data collected that most of the respondents’ family are classified to be minimum wage earners.

In the study conducted by Bower and Griffin (2011) determined the parental involvement of parents in high poverty and high minority where it was proven that there are low parents’ attendance despite the efforts of the school to include them in activities. This may imply that parents of low income have tendencies of low attendance in school events and activities.

Likewise, this result was supported by the study of Williams and Sanchez (2011) where they believe that poverty and lack of financial resources are barriers to parental involvement. This may imply that communications of parents to the school for their children’s activities and academic progress may be hindered due to financial constraints.

Table 8. Respondent’s level of parental involvement as to Parenting

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. My parent explains difficult ideas which I can’t understand.	2.93	.769	Often Involved
2. There are supplementary materials/resources on our house.	3.08	.861	Often Involved
3. My parents consulted me about the plans of the family.	3.16	.907	Often Involved
4. Reading books is a regular activity in our home.	2.43	.782	Rarely Involved
5. My parent establishes a comforting atmosphere when I’m upset.	2.72	.877	Often Involved
Overall	2.86	.496	Often Involved

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Involved); 2.50-3.49 (Often Involved); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Involved); 1.0-1.49 (Never Involved)

Illustrated on Table 8 are the data collected in terms of the level of parental involvement as perceived by the student-respondents, it was shown that parents are often involve when it comes to parenting as it collected an overall mean of 2.86 and standard deviation of 0.496 . With the data gathered, it could be perceived that item statement 3 My parents consulted me about the plans of the family obtained the highest mean of 3.16 which is interpreted as often involved. Meanwhile, it could be seen on the table that item statement 4 Reading books is a regular activity in our home has the least garnered mean with 2.43 and verbal interpretation of rarely involved.

This signifies that reading is not part of the daily parent – child activity at home hence, this does not imply that parents are not involve in their child’s life when they are not routinely spending time for reading along with their kids.

It could also be noted that item statement 5 My parents establish a comforting atmosphere when I’m upset garnered a 2.72 mean interpreted as often involved. This indicates that the parents of the students are not just physically but also emotionally present when their child badly needs them especially in their teenage years when they are highly emotional and unpredictable.

Table 9. Respondent’s level of parental involvement as to Communicating

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. My parent attends parent-teacher conferences to discuss matter about my behavior.	2.91	.933	Often Involved
2. My parent has constant communication to my teachers.	2.90	.772	Often Involved
3. My parent makes time when teachers call for conference about my learning improvement.	3.01	.980	Often Involved
4. My parent consults my teacher about my learning progress.	2.67	.877	Often Involved
5. My parent constantly visits my teachers whenever needed.	2.47	1.000	Rarely Involved
Overall	2.79	.630	Often Involved

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Involved); 2.50-3.49 (Often Involved); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Involved); 1.0-1.49 (Never Involved)

Table 9 depicts data on parental involvement in terms of communicating. Presented on the table are the highest mean obtained to the least of the mean computed. It could be noted that item statement 1 My parent attends parent – teacher conferences to discuss matter about my behavior reached 2.91 mean and interpreted as often involved. Hence, there is still an undeniable high number of parents who never participated in schools’ activities for their children because of several valid reasons. This is still proven as item statement 5 My parent constantly visits my teachers whenever needed received a mean of 2.47 which elicits a verbal interpretation of rarely involved.

Further, it could be gleaned from the table that item statement 3 My parent makes time when teachers call for conference about my learning improvement rank first as it obtained the highest mean of 3.01 verbally interpreted as often involved. This could be reflected through parents’ active participation in school’s card giving and parents’ meeting which allows parents and teachers conference regarding the students’ grade and behavior in school. Overall, when it comes to communicating parents were often involved with a weighted mean and standard deviation of 2.79 and 0.630 accordingly.

These results were further supported by the study of Lopez et al. (2011) where they noted that parents show their parental involvement as a support to their academic achievement. These could be elicited through communicating with teachers when necessary and by assisting them with homework and attending parent-teacher conferences. These data help the researcher conclude that communication of parents with the teachers and the school is essential to students’ progress.

Table 10. Respondent’s level of parental involvement as to Volunteering

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. My parent participates in community and family social activities in my school (e.g., sports games, plays, carnivals).	2.19	.895	Rarely Involved
2. My parent willingly involves in school activities like conferences, meetings and assemblies.	2.83	.877	Often Involved
3. My parent feels very comfortable visiting my school.	2.79	.844	Often Involved
4. In the past 12 months my parent has attended activities at my child’s school several times (e.g., fun nights, performances, awards nights).	2.51	1.030	Often Involved
5. In the past 12 months my parent volunteered at my school at least 3 times.	2.36	.927	Rarely Involved
Overall	2.54	.563	Often Involved

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Involved); 2.50-3.49 (Often Involved); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Involved); 1.0-1.49 (Never Involved)

Illustrated in Table 10 are the data gathered by the researcher in parental involvement specifically volunteering. It could be observed that item statement 2 My parent willingly involves in school activities like conferences, meetings and assemblies gained the highest mean of 2.83 which is interpreted as often involved. Hence, the least mean garnered is for item statement 1 My parent participates in

community and family social activities in my school (e.g., sports games, plays, carnivals) with 2.19 mean interpreted as rarely involved. Likewise, item statement 5 In the past 12 months my parent volunteered at my school at least 3 times also obtained rarely involved verbal interpretation with 2.36 mean computed. These results may signify that parents are not actively volunteering in schools specially that many school activities are during weekdays where parents are also at work.

In summary, when it comes to volunteering, parents were often involved as it has a composite mean of 2.54 and standard deviation of 0.563. Parents' involvement as to volunteering was supported by Lopez et al. (2011), as it showed that parents' involvement in school activities such as volunteering allowed the parents to get more involved to students' academic life and know the get acquainted with the school stakeholders. Lai and Vadeboncoeur (2012) supported this result as they claim that parental involvement encompasses many constructs of school such as engagement like attending parent-teacher conferences and contributing to extracurricular activities. These are classified as volunteering as parents exert their efforts to attend to their child. They also noted that the failure of parental involvement in school is also a failure to increase students' academic growth.

Table 11. *Respondent's level of parental involvement as to Learning at Home*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. My parent set and plot my study schedule.	2.66	1.027	Often Involved
2. My parent monitors my study habits.	2.98	.864	Often Involved
3. My parent advises me to focus and spend more time on difficult subjects.	3.17	.975	Often Involved
4. My parent helps me with my academic skills or activities where they find it difficult.	2.97	.893	Often Involved
5. My parent helps me doing my activities.	2.48	.870	Rarely Involved
Overall	2.85	.635	Often Involved

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Involved); 2.50-3.49 (Often Involved); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Involved); 1.0-1.49 (Never Involved)

Table 11 illustrates the data on parental involvement specifically for learning at home, where it garnered an overall mean of 2.85 interpreted as often involved. It could be gleaned from the table that item statement 3 My parent advises me to focus and spend more time on difficult subjects ranked highest as it obtained the mean of 3.17 which is interpreted as often involved. Meanwhile, least on the rank is item statement 5 My parent helps me in doing my activities as it gained the mean of 2.48 verbally interpreted as rarely involved. With these data, it could be implied that parents are still involved with their children's learning hence are allowing them to independently learn by not helping them in doing activities they could do on their own. This is supported by the results obtained on item statement 1 My parent set and plot my study schedule with the mean of 2.66 with verbal interpretation of often involved. It was revealed that parental involvement in terms of learning at home garnered an interpretation of often involved with a weighted mean of 2.85.

In the study of Nierva (2009), they noted that there is still a need to promote parent active involvement specifically in child's learning at home and school. This gives importance to parental involvement in the form of learning at home as it is believed that in order to facilitate a home-school partnership, policies to guide practices regarding home-school collaboration at national, regional, division and school levels must be developed. This means that parents must also be guided on how to guide their children in learning at home where it calls for school and teacher involvement. Likewise, Arriero (2006) stated that parents generally influence the home environment in terms of creating a learning environment for their children. This justifies that involvement of parents in creating a good learning environment at home is essential in bringing positive outcome for students.

Table 12. *Respondent's level of parental involvement as to Decision Making*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. My parent never doubted about my legal rights as a student.	2.87	.861	Often Involved
2. My parent has made suggestions to my teachers about how to help me learn.	2.28	.996	Rarely Involved
3. My parent knows the laws governing schools well.	2.89	.863	Often Involved
4. In the past 12 months my parent attended several school board meetings.	2.63	.861	Often Involved
5. My parent thinks multiple times on their decisions which are related to my education.	3.18	.821	Often Involved
Overall	2.77	.506	Often Involved

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Involved); 2.50-3.49 (Often Involved); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Involved); 1.0-1.49 (Never Involved)

Depicted on Table 12 are the data on parental involvement in terms of decision making. As presented, item statement 5 My parent thinks multiple times on their decisions which are related to my education obtained the highest mean of

3.18 and interpreted as often involved. Least on the rank is item statement 2 My parent has made suggestions to my teachers about how to help me learn as it garnered a mean of 2.28 verbally interpreted as rarely involved. These data signify that parents are entrusting their child's learning process to their teachers but are significantly active in decision making relative to their child's welfare. This particularly exhibits parents' involvement in their child's learning. It was revealed that parents were often involved in terms of decision making as it has an overall mean of 2.77 and a standard deviation of 0.506.

This is supported by the study conducted by Gulcan and Duran (2018) where they claimed that there is a positive impact of parental involvement in decision making hence there are still some ambiguity how and what level parents must involve in decision making process. This particularly imply the decision making of the parents in terms of their child's learning and learning process. Hence, Dunn (2012) claimed the importance of adding parents to the decision- making process in education also provides accountability and is influential in the action of all stakeholders.

Table 13. *Respondent's level of parentzal involvement as to Collaborating with Community*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. My parent talk with other parents frequently about educational issues.	2.58	.987	Often Involved
2. My parent attends community programs (e.g., community theatre) regularly.	2.58	.901	Often Involved
3. If I am having trouble in school my parent would not know how to get extra help for me.	2.25	.880	Rarely Involved
4. My parent knows about many programs for youth in our community.	2.85	.869	Often Involved
5. My parent build connections with other co-parents to be updated with school activities.	3.00	.932	Often Involved
Overall	2.65	.593	Often Involved

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Involved); 2.50-3.49 (Often Involved); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Involved); 1.0-1.49 (Never Involved)

Table 13 presents the data on parental involvement in terms of collaborating with community. The data presents a significant importance of parents' active participation and involvement on matters relative to community relations and connections that would welfare their child. It could be gleaned from the table that item statement 5 My parent build connections with other co-parents to be updated with school activities received the highest mean of 3.00, interpreted as often involved. This implies that parents' participation and involvement in school are also influenced by other parents where presence of one on an event may also call the presence of others as they share information regarding important events in school that must be attended. In terms of collaboration, parents were often involved as illustrated by the collected weighted mean of 2.65 and standard deviation of 0.593.

However, item statement 3 If I am having trouble in school my parent would not know how to get extra help for me as it is obtained the mean of 2.25, verbally interpreted as rarely involved. This establishes parents' connection with others that may help them to resolve conflict in school. Leander and Fabella (2020) supports these findings as they claim that school and parents should work in collaboration to bring improvement in the academic performance of the students. Development of one's learning is best achieved when parents and school works hand-in-hand to assure that students are learning. Similarly, parents should not only work with the school but with their co- parents also.

Table 14. *Summary of Parental Involvement in terms of:*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Parenting	2.86	.496	Often Involved
Communicating	2.79	.630	Often Involved
Volunteering	2.54	.563	Often Involved
Learning at Home	2.85	.635	Often Involved
Decision Making	2.77	.506	Often Involved
Overall	2.76	.570	Often Involved

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Involved); 2.50-3.49 (Often Involved); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Involved); 1.0-1.49 (Never Involved)

Table 14 illustrates the summary of parental involvement including its indicators. It was revealed that parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home and decision making garnered a mean of 2.86, 2.79, 2.54, 2.85 and 2.77 and corresponding standard deviation of 0.496, 0.630, 0.563, 0.635 and 0.506 respectively all interpreted as often involved. In summary, parents are often involved as it garnered an overall mean of 2.76 and standard deviation of 0.70.

Table 15. *Perception on Parental Encouragement*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. My parent support me in participating in my academic and extracurricular activities.	3.42	.806	Often Practiced
2. Throughout my youth and adolescence, my parent supported and encouraged me.	3.36	.798	Often Practiced
3. My parent provides words of encouragement or praise for my achievements or efforts.	3.30	.759	Often Practiced
4. My parent acknowledges and celebrate my milestone no matter how small.	3.00	.876	Often Practiced
5. My parent support me during challenging and difficult times.	3.35	.880	Often Practiced
Overall	3.29	.647	Often Practiced

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Practiced); 2.50-3.49 (Often Practiced); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Practiced); 1.0-1.49 (Never Practiced)

Illustrated on Table 15 are the respondents' response of parental encouragement where it garnered an overall mean of 3.29 interpreted as often practiced. It could be gleaned on the table that item statement 1 My parent support me in participating in my academic and extracurricular activities received the highest mean of 3.42 interpreted as often practiced. Hence, least on the rank is item statement 4 My parent acknowledges and celebrate my milestone no matter how small with the mean of 3.00. Though it is the least on the items, it still presents active involvement of parents as it is interpreted often practiced.

Significantly, it was also found that item statement 3 My parent provides words of encouragement or praise for my achievements or efforts has the high mean of 3.30 implying often involvement on their child. This also means that parents' way of showing their support and involvement to their child is through words.

Supporting this finding is the study of Gonzales – DeHass et al (2005) where they found that when parents are involved in their children's school and academic motivation, achievement is increasing. This could also signify that parents' support and motivation on students' active involvement in school is an indicator to their academic success.

Table 16. *Perception on Parental Modeling*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. I look up to my parents as good examples to follow in life.	3.55	.687	Always Practiced
2. My parent has the qualities and behaviors I admire.	3.25	.716	Often Practiced
3. My decision-making and behavior have been impacted by the actions of my parents.	3.01	.772	Often Practiced
4. I believe that my parents have contributed my over-all development and well-being.	3.22	.760	Often Practiced
5. My parent has positive behavior and interactions in our household during my childhood.	3.29	.795	Often Practiced
Overall	3.26	.500	Often Practiced

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Practiced); 2.50-3.49 (Often Practiced); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Practiced); 1.0-1.49 (Never Practiced)

Depicted in Table 16 are the data on responses on parental modeling. It could be observed that item statement 1 I look up to my parents as good examples to follow in life obtained the highest mean of 3.55 which is verbally interpreted as always practiced. This signified that students always see their parents as their role model that set examples to follow. This is also supported by the results obtained on item statement 3 My decision-making and behavior have been impacted by the actions of my parents as it received the mean of 3.01. Despite receiving the lowest mean, it is still interpreted as often practiced which implies that students believe that their behavior is influenced by how they see their parents behave and act. Overall, parental modelling is often practiced as it was shown that a weighted mean of 3.26 was computed.

Relative to parent modelling, Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) claimed in their study that parents' cognition about their role is a major contributor to their willingness to engage in supportive parenting. Educational and occupational aspirations of parents are also associated with the way parents shape their children's activities, time and learning environment. This signifies that parents are children's role model and are contributory to how they act and behave as they shape their activities and learning.

Table 17 presents data on parental reinforcement. It could be gleaned on the table that item statement 5 My parents show their support by working with me to develop ideas for strategies or solutions has the highest mean of 3.33 which is verbally interpreted as often

practiced. Hence, item statement 4 My parents have a set system of rewards for good deeds or accomplishments earned the lowest mean of 3.22 but still interpreted as often practiced. The data imply that parents provide reinforcement to their children in various forms. Parental reinforcement garnered an overall mean of 3.12 interpreted as often practiced.

Table 17. *Perception on Parental Reinforcement*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. When I accomplish something, my parents verbally congratulate me or offer encouraging words.	3.10	.835	Often Practiced
2. My parent typically express positive reinforcement.	3.08	.837	Often Practiced
3. My parent encourages me in my endeavors.	3.19	.677	Often Practiced
4. My parents have a set system of rewards for good deeds or accomplishments.	3.01	.798	Often Practiced
5. My parents show their support by working with me to develop ideas for strategies or solutions.	3.22	.799	Often Practiced
Overall	3.12	.518	Often Practiced

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Practiced); 2.50-3.49 (Often Practiced); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Practiced); 1.0-1.49 (Never Practiced)

Notably, it was also found that parents reinforce students' behavior and performance in school through words. It was proven by the results obtained on item statement 1 When I accomplish something, my parents verbally congratulate me or offer encouraging words with the mean of 3.10, interpreted as often practiced.

These findings were supported by the study conducted by Lai and Vadeboncoeur (2012) where they stated that parental involvement should include providing intrinsic and extrinsic motivation as it would encourage students' achievement. This means that parents words are reinforcements for students to perform better in school.

Table 18. *Perception on Parental Instructions*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. My parent provides clarity of instruction during my childhood.	3.38	.648	Often Practiced
2. My parent typically provides specific details and steps when giving instruction.	3.24	.754	Often Practiced
3. I believe that the instructions of my parents helped me navigate different aspects of my life.	3.32	.695	Often Practiced
4. My parent typically responds when I struggle or face difficulties in following their instructions	3.23	.737	Often Practiced
5. My parent gives an illustration of a particular set of instructions that I found useful and significant.	3.07	.756	Often Practiced
Overall	3.24	.521	Often Practiced

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Always Practiced); 2.50-3.49 (Often Practiced); 1.50-2.49 (Rarely Practiced); 1.0-1.49 (Never Practiced)

Table 18 illustrates garnered responses on parental instructions whereas it could be noted that there is an overall mean of 3.24 which is interpreted as often practiced. It could also be seen that item statement 1 My parent provides clarity of instruction during my childhood garnered the highest weighted mean of 3.38, verbally interpreted as often practiced. Hence, item statement 5 My parent gives an illustration of a particular set of instructions that I found useful and significant achieved a mean of 3.07, interpreted as often practiced and least on the rank. This signify that despite being the least, it is clear that parents are still consistent in providing instructions to their children as part of the parental involvement. An overall mean of 3.24 was obtained by parental instructions interpreted as often practiced.

This is supported by the findings of Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (2005) where they stated that parental instruction materializes in social interactions between parent and child during involvement activities as they engage in shared thinking related to learning strategies, processes, outcomes, and engage in educational strategies. This means that parental instructions are of great help on students' academic progress and activities. In the context of this study, parental instructions will aid learners as they perform better and acquire new skills in Cookery.

Table 19 illustrates the summary of parental mechanisms including its indicators. It was revealed that parental encouragement, parental modelling, parental reinforcement and parental instructions garnered a mean of 3.29, 3.26, 3.12 and 3.24 and corresponding standard deviation of 0.647, 0.500, 0.518, and 0.521 respectively all interpreted as often practiced. In summary, parental mechanism is often practiced as it garnered an overall mean of 3.23 and standard deviation of 0.547.

Table 19. *Summary of Parental Mechanisms*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
Parental Encouragement	3.29	.647	Often Practiced
Parental Modelling	3.26	.500	Often Practiced
Parental Reinforcement	3.12	.518	Often Practiced
Parental Instructions	3.24	.521	Often Practiced
Overall	3.23	.547	Often Practiced

Table 20 composes of data collected on the respondents' level of confidence. It could be observed from the table that on the assessment of the indicators of self-confidence, students are perceived to be confident as proven by the 3.00 overall mean garnered on students' response. Significantly, it was proven by the 3.41 highest mean obtained on item statement 8 I have more respect for myself which is interpreted as confident. Meanwhile, item statement 13 I have the capacity to handle unexpected situations in my certain task placed the least on the rank as it achieved the mean of 2.86 verbally interpreted as confident. This may imply doubt experienced by the respondents when facing difficult tasks.

Table 20. *Respondent's self- confidence level*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. On the whole, I am satisfied with myself.	3.14	.725	Confident
2. At times I think I am so good at all	2.90	.732	Confident
3. I feel that I have a number of good qualities.	2.95	.657	Confident
4. I can do things as well as most other people.	2.96	.695	Confident
5. I feel I have much to be proud of.	3.03	.688	Confident
6. I certainly feel useful at times.	2.97	.846	Confident
7. I feel that I'm a person of worth.	2.95	.744	Confident
8. I have more respect for myself	3.41	.683	Confident
9. All in all, I am inclined to think that I am successful.	3.10	.704	Confident
10. I take a positive attitude toward myself.	3.13	.787	Confident
11. I can perform anything pertaining to my area of expertise.	2.93	.671	Confident
12. I am self-assured in my abilities.	3.03	.643	Confident
13. I have the capacity to handle unexpected situations in my certain task.	2.86	.766	Confident
14. I am capable of doing anything on my own without assistance.	2.75	.796	Confident
15. I have faith in my capacity to think outside the box and develop new concepts in my field of expertise.	2.95	.730	Confident
Overall	3.00	.424	Confident

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Very Confident); 2.50-3.49 (Confident); 1.50-2.49 (Somewhat Confident); 1.0-1.49 (Not Confident)

Table 20 composes of data collected on the respondents' level of confidence. It could be observed from the table that on the assessment of the indicators of self-confidence, students are perceived to be confident as proven by the 3.00 overall mean garnered on students' response. Significantly, it was proven by the 3.41 highest mean obtained on item statement 8 I have more respect for myself which is interpreted as confident. Meanwhile, item statement 13 I have the capacity to handle unexpected situations in my certain task placed the least on the rank as it achieved the mean of 2.86 verbally interpreted as confident. This may imply doubt experienced by the respondents when facing difficult tasks.

In general, respondents responded confident on item statement 1 On the whole, I am satisfied with myself as it obtained the mean of 3.14. Likewise, they also answered confident on item statement 9 All in all, I am inclined to think that I am successful as it garnered the mean of 3.10. In summary, respondents were confident as revealed in the overall mean collected 3.00.

With the data obtained relative students' self-confidence, it was supported by the study of Wrieden et al. (2007) that learning and using cooking skills and food skills have been positively linked to cooking confidence, cooking ability, food safety, reduction in food waste and time spent in meal preparation. This confidence is skills also brings self- confidence to the student as they to academic tasks in school.

Table 21 depicts data collected, computed and tabulated in relation to the respondents' learning outcome in terms of their quarterly test. It could be noted that by scores most of the student correctly answered 19-24 items as it obtained 54% of the total number of items. Secondly, 27% of the respondents garnered 13-18 correct items in their quarterly examination. It could also be observed that there are still few numbers of students receiving 0- 6 and 7-12 scores in their quarterly examination composing 1% and 2% of the total number of respondents respectively. With the data obtained, it could be implied that average scores are received by the students in their quarterly test.

Table 21. Respondent's outcome in terms of Quarterly Test

Scores	Frequency	Percent	VI
25-30	16	16.0	Excellent
19-24	54	54.0	Very Good
13-18	27	27.0	Good
7-12	2	2.0	Fair
0-6	1	1.0	Poor
Total	100	100	

Legend: 25-30 (Excellent); 19-24 (Very Good); 13-18 (Good); 7-12 (Fair); 0-6 (Poor)

In the study of Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (2005), students performed on the average in examination or quarterly assessment as they are assisted by various factors which includes technology access, resources and academic support. On the other hand, Wrieden et al. (2007) argued that some students' academic scores were affected by social media and distractions. Relative to scores obtained, it was found by Topor et al., (2010) that achievement test scores were influenced by increased perception of cognitive competence which were significantly related to parental involvement. This signified that students' scores in their quarterly test may be affected by their parents' parental involvement which then increases their cognitive competence.

Table 22. Learners' Outcome in the Performance Task

Rating	Scores	Preparation / Cutting		Mixing Techniques		Cooking Techniques		Creativity / Presentation		Work Habits / Kitchen Safety		Interpretation
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Above 89	9-10	29	29	30	30	20	20	1	1	32	32	Excellent
85-89	7-8	56	56	52	52	53	53	54	54	41	41	Very Good
80-84	5-6	8	8	11	11	20	20	34	34	21	21	Good
75-79	3-4	7	7	7	7	7	7	11	11	6	6	Fair
70-74	0-2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Poor
Total		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	

Table 22 contains data of the respondents' outcome performance task in Cookery. It could be observed from the table that work habits or kitchen safety has the highest frequency among all the criteria where 32% of the respondent garnered a rating of 89 and above interpreted as excellent. However, the least among the criteria which garnered the lowest number of rating above 89 is creativity and presentation. On the other hand, none of the respondents got a rating of 70-74 or poor in any criteria.

Consequently, all of the performance tasks for Cookery are accomplished by the respondents as mostly good. These data also imply that students perform well in various areas of the subject particularly on the criteria measured. This result was supported by the works of Wrieden et al. (2007) where among all the skills or knowledge in the cookery, it is basic to know the kitchen safety and the do's and don'ts as it was one of the most essential skills when cooking. Meanwhile, Durisic and Bunijevac (2017) stated that at a young age, parents taught their child first the importance of following the kitchen rules as well as the safety procedures to avoid any untowards incidents.

It may be concluded that students' classroom performance through performance tasks may be influence by various factors such as parental involvement. This conclusion is supported by Topor et al. (2010) by which they stated that parents who have a positive attitude towards their child's education, school and teacher are able to positively influence their child's classroom performance and academic performance in general.

Table 23. Significant relationship between Parental Involvement and Learners' Outcome

Parental Involvement	Quarterly Test	Learner's Outcome Performance Tasks						Overall
		FP/C	MT	CT	CP	H/KS		
Parenting	-.055	-.050	-.038	.057	.120	.053	.028	
Communicating	-.071	-.051	.009	-.030	.054	.026	.000	
Volunteering	-.032	-.023	.033	.064	.038	.089	.044	
Learning at Home	-.048	.069	.100	.138	.228*	.195	.155	
Decision Making	-.099	.059	.115	.168	.141	.187	.144	
Collaboration with Community	.066	.078	.140	.060	.128	.185	.127	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Verbal Interpretation of r-value: +1.0 Perfect positive +/- association +0.8 to +1.0 Very strong +/- association +0.6 to +0.8 Strong +/- association +0.4 to +0.6 Moderate +/- association +0.2 to +0.4 Weak +/- association 0.0 to +0.2 Very weak +/- or no association

Table 23 illustrates data gathered relative to the relationship of learners' outcome and parental involvement. It could be gleaned from the table that there is a significant correlation among variables at 0.01 level of confidence. Meanwhile, there is a very weak association found on the variables learning at home, decision making and collaboration with community. This indicates that students' learning outcomes are affected by parental involvement particularly by parenting, communicating and volunteering.

This was supported by the findings of Gonzalez – DeHass et al., (2005) where they also claim that when parents are involved in their children’s school, academic motivation and achievement increase. This further concludes that it is a contributing factor in improving and promoting students’ achievement. Likewise, it was proven as RimmKaufman and Pianta (2011) stated that parent’s school involvement may lead to more positive academic outcomes in children. This fosters a sense of shared responsibility for children’s education.

Table 24. Significant relationship between Parental Mechanism and Learners’ Outcome

Parental Mechanisms	Quarterly Test	Learner’s Outcome					Overall
		Performance Tasks					
		FP/C	MT	CT	CP	H/KS	
Encouragement	-.220*	-.026	.022	.131	.070	.088	.061
Modelling	-.204*	.021	.076	.116	.124	.117	.097
Reinforcement	-.217*	.036	.095	.158	.178	.182	.139
Instruction	-.270**	.032	.060	.195	.194	.148	.133

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 Verbal Interpretation of r-value: +1.0 Perfect positive +/- association +0.8 to +1.0 Very strong +/- association +0.6 to +0.8 Strong +/- association +0.4 to +0.6 Moderate +/- association +0.2 to +0.4 Weak +/- association 0.0 to +0.2 Very weak +/- or no association

Meanwhile, Table 24 elicits data on the relationship between parental mechanism and quarterly test. With the tabulated data, it could be noted that there is no relationship between the stated variable. It relatively presents negative relationship on encouragement, modeling, reinforcement and instruction. This may imply that despite encouragement of parents as well as modeling, reinforcement and instruction there is still no effect on students’ results on their quarterly examination.

Contradictory to these findings, several studies claim the positive effect of parental mechanism such as parental encouragement, modeling, reinforcement and instructions to students’ academic performance in general. It was found by Martinize-Pons (1996) as cited by Hoover-Dempsey and Sandler (2005) that a child who is encouraged to persist to do so will be more likely to succeed in engaging in school work than a child who is not. This would most probably help students to persist in their examinations, performance tasks and their academic success in general.

Table 25. Significant relationship between self-confidence and learners’ outcome

Self Confidence	Quarterly Test	Learner’s Outcome					Overall
		Performance Tasks					
		FP/C	MT	CT	CP	H/KS	
	.000	.001	.028	.060	.121	.073	.059

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 Verbal Interpretation of r-value: +1.0 Perfect positive +/- association +0.8 to +1.0 Very strong +/- association +0.6 to +0.8 Strong +/- association +0.4 to +0.6 Moderate +/- association +0.2 to +0.4 Weak +/- association 0.0 to +0.2 Very weak +/- or no association

Table 25 presents the data obtained on the relationship between self- confidence and learners’ outcome. It could be observed from the table that there is no significant relationship between self-confidence and learners’ outcome. This signifies that the students’ self-confidence may not affect learners’ outcome, be it in their quarterly examination or their performance tasks. It could also reflect that even if the students’ self-confidence is high, it would not dictate their learning success.

Table 26. Significant relationship between Parental Involvement in students’ self-confidence

Parental Involvement	Self Confidence
Parenting	.335**
Communicating	.224*
Volunteering	.204*
Learning at Home	.374**
Decision Making	.307**
Collaboration with Community	.381**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 Verbal Interpretation of r-value: +1.0 Perfect positive +/- association +0.8 to +1.0 Very strong +/- association +0.6 to +0.8 Strong +/- association +0.4 to +0.6 Moderate +/- association +0.2 to +0.4 Weak +/- association 0.0 to +0.2 Very weak +/- or no association

Table 26 illustrates data on the relationship between students’ self- confidence and parental involvement. It could be noted that there is a significant relationship between variables when computed with 0.01 and 0.05 level of confidence. Hence, it could be observed that the association of the variables has weak to very weak correlation. This may signify that parental involvement may affect the self-confidence of the students.

This conclusion is supported by the findings of Wang and Sheik-Khalil (2014) as they claimed that increased parental involvement is associated with gains in cognition and language and social-emotional development as well as children's self-esteem, emotional self-regulation, and self-perceptions of academic competence. This means that parental involvement affects self-confidence of the students along with their belief of their skills academically.

Table 27. *Significant relationship between Parental Involvement and Parental Mechanism in students' self-confidence*

Parental Mechanisms	Self Confidence
Encouragement	.434**
Modeling	.392**
Reinforcement	.532**
Instruction	.423**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
Verbal Interpretation of r-value: +1.0 Perfect positive +/- association +0.8 to +1.0 Very strong +/- association +0.6 to +0.8 Strong +/- association +0.4 to +0.6 Moderate +/- association +0.2 to +0.4 Weak +/- association 0.0 to +0.2 Very weak +/- or no association

Significantly, Table 27 depicts the tabulated data on the relationship of parental mechanisms and students' self-confidence. It could be gleaned on the data that there is a significant relationship between the variables when computed with 0.01 and 0.05 level of confidence. Notably, the correlation was from weak to moderate correlation. Despite weak correlation, it could still be implied that parental mechanisms affect the self-confidence of the students.

With the uniqueness of the present study, the researcher found no similar result as presented. This signify that no supporting literature and studies are conducted yet to further justify the connection and correlation between parental.

Furthermore, the absence of relationship between self-confidence and the learners' outcomes, the researcher was not able to perform mediation analysis on the effect of self-confidence on parental involvement and mechanism to learners' outcome.

Conclusions

Based from the results and finding, the researcher concluded the following:

A significant relationship among variables were observed however weak relationship between learning at home with creativity and presentation was determined. Moreover, negative relationship between parental mechanisms and quarterly tests was revealed. Additionally, no significant relationship between learning outcomes and self-confidence was seen. Lastly, a weak to moderate significant relationship between self-confidence and parental involvement and parental mechanisms was exhibited. The results led to the failure of acceptance of the null hypotheses.

From the conclusions presented, the researcher would like to offer the following recommendations;

Based from the results, it was revealed that parental involvement to the students were regarded as often involve. Since parents show involvement on students' school activities and event, it is suggested for the parents to keep nourishing their role on their child's education. Though often involved, parents may exert more time in participating to school activities despite of busy schedule.

Parental involvement and mechanisms shows indirect significant relationship to learners' outcome. Due to this it is recommended for the parents to keep on assisting their child and attend to their needs most especially when completing their tasks as it will help them to be motivated and seek for better learning outcomes.

Though no significant relationship between learner's outcome and self- confidence, it is important to boost the students' moral and confidence when doing activities or outputs as it may help in building their personality in doing things.

It was revealed that significant relationship exist between self-confidence and parental involvement and mechanism. Due to this notion, parents should be vigilant in monitoring and involving themselves to their child's personality development. Parents should establish an open communication to help their child in honing their interpersonal and intrapersonal abilities.

Schools may spearhead activities involving parents and students in order to build collaborative partnership and open communication between students and parents. Seminars on parenting may be proposed so as to promote positive parenting among parents or guardians.

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